

Integrating agent-based disease, mobility, and wastewater models: Dealing with differences in spatiotemporal resolutions

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Abstract

Wastewater-based epidemiology was utilized during the COVID-19 outbreak to monitor the circulation of SARS-CoV-2, as viral RNA can be detected in wastewater. However, wastewater-based epidemiology is limited by the need for additional methods to translate virus concentrations in wastewater to disease prevalence accurately. Combined modelling of SARS-CoV-2 concentrations in wastewater and COVID-19 disease cases is necessary to deepen our understanding, but this requires addressing the technical differences between wastewater and disease models. Here, we develop an integrated agent-based model (ABM) that facilitates analysis in space and time at various temporal resolutions, includes population mobility, and is sufficiently generic for different types of infectious diseases or pathogens. In developing this ABM, we created a disease and domestic wastewater model, which incorporated mobility and employed an event-based approach to address the differences in the spatiotemporal resolutions of the models. We then used the integrated ABM in a COVID-19 use case. Our results show that the integrated model can reveal spatiotemporal patterns consistent with those documented in the literature for each model. The integrated model replicates the

26 epidemic curve for diseases and can show the daily number of infections per household,
27 enabling monitoring of spatial patterns. The model reveals that population mobility
28 decreased during the disease outbreak when patients remained home. Additionally, the
29 model can produce curves of infected wastewater production over time and simulate the flow
30 of infected wastewater in the sewage network. The model addresses differences between
31 resolutions, provides new insights, and has the potential to support early warning of
32 pandemics.

33 **Keywords:** Agent-based model, epidemiology, surveillance, outbreak, geospatial.

34 **1. Introduction**

35 Water-based epidemiology is an emerging surveillance method with great potential for
36 detecting infectious diseases at an early stage (Zhu et al., 2021). Detecting pathogens via
37 wastewater is particularly useful in monitoring disease outbreaks when other disease
38 monitoring techniques are unavailable. Wastewater surveillance is common for detecting
39 water-borne diseases such as cholera, but it was applied globally during the COVID-19
40 pandemic. Although continuous wastewater monitoring is feasible in some countries,
41 intermittent sampling is the only option in others. The results of intermittent sampling are
42 fragmented, which presents multiple challenges in capturing disease outbreaks. Infected
43 wastewater samples indicate the prevalence of the disease (e.g., SARS-CoV-2 genome copies)
44 and not the number of infected inhabitants, which makes it difficult to interpret the
45 significance of the results and compare between multiple locations (Faraway et al., 2022).
46 Studying the dynamics of infected wastewater, such as infected urine and stool particles, is
47 challenging because of the mixed composition. Nevertheless, this approach is beneficial
48 because wastewater carries the virus, significantly increasing the chances of capturing the

49 prevalence of a disease (Chen et al., 2020; Cerrada-Romero et al., 2022). The complications
50 in interpreting the significance of sampled wastewater hinder the design of effective
51 wastewater surveillance in sewer systems and the description of disease outbreaks (Martin
52 et al., 2023; NASEM, 2023). Models have the potential to simulate the disease in wastewater
53 and relate it to the actual number of infections in an area. They can also support the
54 representation of infected wastewater dynamics, optimize the design of where and when to
55 sample wastewater for early disease detection, and indicate mitigation measures to reduce
56 the spread of a disease based on the interpretation of the wastewater sampling. However,
57 this requires the integration of disease spread, population mobility, and wastewater models.
58 Most wastewater models focus on the physicochemical (SPC) processes within the sewer
59 (Freni et al., 2010; Verdaguer et al., 2014; Cook et al., 2018; Petrucci et al., 2019), omitting
60 the impact from the human population (Jia et al., 2021), which makes them incompatible with
61 disease spread modeling. SPC models do not include the population dynamics in space and
62 time, such as mobility and the use of water appliances, even when modeling the spatial
63 variations of pollutants (Chen et al., 2019). SPC models are predominantly designed to predict
64 and quantify wastewater pollutants (Maruéjols et al., 2014). Agent-based models (ABMs)
65 are a family of models that allow for more effective modeling of wastewater by using agent-
66 based principles, which are better suited for integrating disease dynamics (Augustijn et al.,
67 2016). ABMs are computational simulations of individual, dynamic, and adaptive behavior
68 agents with multiple characteristics that provide interactions between the agents and their
69 environment (McLane et al., 2011). ABMs enable testing of different scenarios based on
70 agents that dynamically interact in space and time, considering both agent and environment
71 characteristics. Since ABMs are bottom-up models that focus on micro-level autonomous
72 interacting agents, they allow the modeling of human wastewater production in space and

73 time (Darbandsari et al., 2020; Oliva-Felipe et al., 2021; Truszkowska et al., 2021; Ngo et al.,
74 2022; Assaad et al., 2023). Wastewater ABMs focus on modeling social and organizational
75 components, including the adoption of technologies, conflict resolution, policies, testing
76 infrastructure, and maintenance programs (Panebianco and Pahl-Wostl, 2006; Darbandsari et
77 al., 2020; Ngo et al., 2022; Assaad et al., 2023). There are some examples in the literature of
78 the use of wastewater ABMs to model spatiotemporal pollutants, i.e., a model of industrial
79 wastewater from pig farms to map pollutant loads (Ngo et al., 2022). A domestic wastewater
80 (DW) ABM, which was used to simulate the spatiotemporal dynamics of wastewater
81 production (DelaPaz-Ruiz et al., 2023), is the closest example to make an integration of a
82 wastewater ABM and a disease ABM. In particular, the DW ABM can track multiple types of
83 wastewater events such as stool production and motion in the sewage produced at the
84 individual level, with the potential to reflect population mobility, the spread of disease, and
85 the infected wastewater.

86 Disease ABMs can reproduce epidemic curve patterns of outbreaks (Barat et al., 2021;
87 Truszkowska et al., 2021). They can also explicitly model human interactions (at various
88 spatial locations) and the resulting disease diffusion. There are two other important
89 components in disease AMBs: population mobility and interaction. Although population
90 mobility is relevant for interactions that initiate an outbreak, not all models explicitly
91 integrate mobility (Barat et al., 2021; Truszkowska et al., 2021). Mobility can be modeled
92 either by allowing agents to move randomly or by using empirical commuting data to simulate
93 their movements. In this case, agent commuting is linked to activities such as commuting to
94 school or work. A single disease ABM may contain many different activities linked to multiple
95 commuting networks (Augustijn et al., 2022). Interactions can occur when agents are at the
96 same location, but this is often insufficient. At many locations, a grouping of agents is needed

97 to correctly represent interaction, for example, based on school age groups. Susceptible-
98 Infected-Recovered (SIR) models are commonly used to simulate disease diffusion (McMahon
99 and Robb, 2020).

100 Integrating a disease ABM with a wastewater ABM and incorporating population mobility is
101 necessary but challenging. In particular, differences in temporal resolution introduce
102 significant complexity. Other challenges include designing a system that effectively schedules
103 agent actions over time, and validating outputs when data are insufficient (Heppenstall et al.,
104 2021a; An et al., 2021). An ABM integrating disease, mobility, and wastewater should include
105 the following components: inhabitant agent states (such as infection status and sick leave),
106 agent mobility, disease transmission, wastewater production, and wastewater flow through
107 the sewage network. Wastewater models work with fine temporal intervals representing
108 wastewater variability over time, which supports the development of wastewater sampling
109 strategies. Event-based modeling facilitates models with fine temporal intervals. The DW
110 ABM (DelaPaz-Ruíz et al., 2023) is event-based, meaning that agent actions are based on
111 defining events at specific times. In the DW ABM, inhabitant agents can produce a wastewater
112 event at any point in time (Torabi et al., 2023). In discrete-event DW ABMs, inhabitant agents
113 schedule every action, such as using the toilet or going home at specific times. A discrete-
114 event ABM can make the simulated temporality more accurate and detailed than a tick- or
115 timestep-based ABM approach. This detailed temporality means that a discrete-event DW
116 ABM can deliver results at multiple temporal intervals, e.g., 6, 12, 30, or 60 minutes. This
117 granularity is particularly useful when designing wastewater sampling schemes. In contrast,
118 disease ABMs are often daily representations divided into time block executions (ticks or
119 timesteps), which are tracked at a 24-hour temporal resolution (Barat et al., 2021;
120 Truszkowska et al., 2021). Dividing days into blocks representing various activities is a

121 common approach in modeling ABM interactions (Heppenstall et al., 2021a; An et al., 2021).
122 This requires a small number of timesteps per day (three or four) and delivers daily outputs.
123 However, this resolution does not match the multi-temporal variability of wastewater. The
124 temporal resolution differences between models must be solved to integrate mobility,
125 disease, and domestic wastewater (DDW) ABMs.

126 In response to the above-mentioned need, we developed a DDW model. This model supports
127 the study of multiple diseases by integrating a disease ABM with a validated DW ABM that
128 includes population mobility (DelaPaz-Ruiz et al., 2023) while addressing differences in
129 temporal resolution. We present:

- 130 • a generic disease and domestic wastewater model that integrates population mobility,
- 131 • a DDW developed with discrete events to address differences in resolution between
132 the models, and
- 133 • a demonstration of the integration of the models in a COVID-19 outbreak use case to
134 illustrate its usefulness for disease surveillance.

135 Section 2 below summarizes the functionality of the DDW and its three model components:
136 disease, mobility, and wastewater. Section 3 explains the integration of the three models,
137 introducing discrete events to address resolution differences and detailing the required data
138 postprocessing. Section 4 outlines a use case of the DDW, presenting epidemic curves,
139 population mobility trends during the outbreak, and a series of maps depicting the spread of
140 infected wastewater throughout the sewer system. Finally, we discuss our findings and the
141 limitations of the DDW, suggest areas for future work, and detail our conclusions.

142 **2. Model**

143 **2.1. General model overview**

144 The DDW model is an ABM simulating interactions between inhabitants (disease diffusion)
145 where inhabitants produce wastewater particle agents, including infected wastewater. This
146 infected wastewater travels over the network to a wastewater plant. The aim of the model is
147 to model disease and wastewater simultaneously. The functionality components of the model
148 are split over three submodels: the disease model, the mobility model, and the wastewater
149 model. These three submodels are explained in detail within section 2. At initialization, a
150 synthetic agent population and geographically explicit environments are loaded. Synthetic
151 inhabitant agents are distributed across houses in the area based on census data, which also
152 provided detailed information on gender, age, occupation, and education for these agents.
153 Based on the census data, these agents attend school or work during the weekdays and spend
154 the remaining part of the day with their household members. Inhabitant agents store their
155 location (home, work, and school) in memory. In addition to the houses, schools, and
156 workplaces, the environment of neighborhood blocks and the sewage network are also
157 loaded. The supplementary material describes the DDW using the ODD (Overview, Design
158 concepts, Details) template provided by Grimm and Ayllón (2020). The DW ABM (DelaPaz-
159 Ruíz et al., 2023) is used as a starting point to integrate the disease and DW ABM, showing
160 the data and description of the case study validated for total suspended solids (TSS), the main
161 indicator linked to stool events. The DDW submodels repeat runs in the same temporal and
162 spatial environment as follows: agent interaction, disease spread, use of domestic water
163 appliances, mobility of inhabitant agents (remaining at home, work, and school), and DW

164 particle motion. The scheduling of processes executes events at dynamic times based on
165 probabilities that depend on the event type. The number of events or actions that each
166 inhabitant agent executes varies. Events primarily follow realistic probabilistic distributions
167 for wastewater (DelaPaz-Ruíz et al., 2023). Disease-related events are described in the
168 following sections. The DDW concurrently captures the number of infected inhabitant agents
169 and their infected wastewater at the locality level as outputs. DDW events can be visualized
170 as a spatiotemporal map series showing neighborhood blocks, households, maintenance
171 holes, and WWTP (catchment level) locations. The status of inhabitants and wastewater
172 agents can be categorized as infected, recovered, or susceptible.

173 **2.2. Disease**

174 The Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) (Duan and Nie, 2022) model has been implemented
175 in this DDW ABM. The parameters of the disease model are shown in Table 1, which can be
176 adapted based on the characteristics of the disease. Agents have a health state that can be
177 either susceptible, infected, or recovered. At the start of the simulation, a number of initial
178 infected cases (N) is generated. After the duration of infection of an inhabitant (D) has elapsed, the
179 infected agent will recover (McMahon and Robb, 2020) and become immune until the end of
180 the simulation. The DDW encapsulates the dynamics of how people commute between home,
181 school, or work locations, reflecting the propagation of the disease throughout the population
182 over time. The disease model includes an interaction component that determines the agents
183 with which an agent has contact. Full interaction is assumed within the household, meaning
184 that agents living in the same household can infect all other agents living in the house. In the
185 cases of school and work, it is important to consider that individuals do not interact with all
186 others present at the same location. When disease transmission requires close contact, we

187 need to sample a subset of agents that can be infected, which is achieved using the
188 *Susceptible-Infected interaction S parameter*. The 'S' parameter indicates how many other
189 agents an individual may contact when their locations overlap, such as in a school. The
190 contacted agents are sampled randomly from the locations that an infected agent visit (i.e.,
191 household, school, or workplace).

192 **2.3. Mobility**

193 Inhabitant agents move to simulate individuals going to school or work and returning home
194 based on working and studying hours, or staying at home, depending on their census data
195 attributes. The modeling components and information linked to mobility are listed in Table 2,
196 which are used to send inhabitants to specific school points and economic points (considered
197 workplaces). For example, Table 2 shows an inhabitant high school agent; the ABM will send
198 the agent to the high school's designated location. Since there are data limitations for
199 mobility, mobility is simulated inside the limits of the locality. In other words, the local
200 population does not leave the locality, and no individuals from the external population travels
201 into the locality.

202 **2.4. Wastewater**

203 Each inhabitant agent will generate wastewater using toilets, water basins, showers, kitchens,
204 and washing machines. Wastewater particles will be generated at the current location of the
205 agent. When an inhabitant agent is infected, the wastewater particle agent will provide the
206 health status of the inhabitant. Wastewater moves via the sewer to the wastewater
207 treatment plant. The DDW simulates the number of infected agents and the spatiotemporal
208 DW loads of the infected stool, representing the main output variables. The DDW allows for

209 the tracking of infected wastewater by simulating the inhabitants' water appliance usage.
210 Each inhabitant agent produces wastewater (hatching a DW particle agent) using water
211 appliances. The DW production is based on distribution probabilities (DelaPaz-Ruíz et al.,
212 2023) that reflect typical daily sequences of water appliance usage for a given date and time.
213 The execution probabilities also contain census-related information. Inhabitant agents store
214 their health status (infected, recovered, or susceptible) and location (home, work, and school)
215 in memory. The water appliances represent basins, kitchens, showers, toilets, and washing
216 machines at their houses. Based on the literature, every single DW particle contains pollutant
217 loads such as TSS. DW particle agents execute flow motion in the sewer, generating particles
218 that move with an average velocity through the pipelines according to the network
219 connectivity. The DWW identifies maintenance holes in the sewage to store relevant data
220 (see supplementary material) as a time series of pollutant loads, providing the DW with
221 temporal variability.

222 **3. Integration**

223 The integration of the three submodels– disease, mobility, and wastewater–in the DDW
224 model is based on the following elements: discrete event simulation (section 3.1), cessation
225 of mobility due to illness, and production of infected wastewater (section 3.2). This
226 integration facilitates monitoring levels of infected wastewater at multiple locations. The DW
227 particle agents demonstrate the integration by storing information about the health condition
228 of inhabitants (infected, recovered, and susceptible), their production (in a block) and dying
229 (in a treatment plant), timestamps, DW quality (TSS), and quantity values. The discrete event
230 simulation enables flexible event scheduling, offering the ABM a clear temporal
231 representation, which facilitates the integration of models with varying temporal resolutions.

232 **3.1. Discrete event**

233 The DDW is developed in NetLogo, a software for ABMs that uses a temporal tick counter for
234 executing procedures. By default NetLogo does not schedule isolated events (or agent
235 actions) in date-time formats (Wilensky, 1999). The standard ABM approach has the limitation
236 of not allowing for precise timing of agents' continuous actions, resulting in the loss of
237 valuable information from aggregated agent rules. As a result, there is an assumption that the
238 actions of all agents occur in a single tick, significantly limiting the simulated spatiotemporal
239 heterogeneity of the DDW phenomena. For instance, the simplified assumption of defining a
240 day as a tick for the DDW is inappropriate. While daily ticks are sufficient for disease ABMs
241 representing an epidemic curve pattern (Mahdizadeh Gharakhanlou and Hooshangi, 2020;
242 Truszkowska et al., 2021), using daily ticks for wastewater production would imply that
243 inhabitants' water usage and the motion of DW particles in the sewer occur simultaneously
244 in a day event, resulting in a flat pattern rather than capturing the high temporal variability
245 of infected DW load patterns across the day. Discrete-event ABMs overcome the
246 oversimplifications of traditional ABMs, which use aggregated tick events. In the DDW,
247 discrete events are the isolated and independent actions agents execute, tracking the exact
248 time. Contrasting with the tick counter, the DDW model uses the NetLogo time extension
249 (Sheppard et al., 2022) to execute discrete events for each inhabitant and DW particle action.
250 The time extension allows dynamic scheduling actions in explicit date-time format, individual
251 temporal actions, and continuous tracking when events occur (Sheppard et al., 2020). As a
252 result, the DDW model does not have a fixed temporal resolution, such as a daily resolution.
253 Instead, each event is temporally and spatially scheduled and recorded. The events follow
254 temporal frequency distributions based on the probability that an agent executes a given

255 event. For instance, the model applies a moderate probability for stool production events
256 throughout the day, particularly after mealtimes. This assumption is based on the likelihood
257 that inhabitants activate their colons following meals, leading to stool production events that
258 generate DW particles with specific TSS concentrations and infection statuses.

259 **3.2. Linking disease, mobility, and wastewater**

260 Figure 1 shows the essential integration between the disease, mobility, and wastewater
261 models. Two processes are crucial for this integration: breaking commuting patterns due to
262 illness and the infection of wastewater particles.

263 Infected inhabitant agents can transmit the disease to other vulnerable inhabitants in their
264 households, workplaces, and schools. The infection event is conditioned to the location
265 coincidence between the infected and susceptible inhabitants. The '*Susceptible-Infected*
266 *interaction (S) parameter*' defines the range of new possible infections that a single infected
267 inhabitant agent can spread to others. The start of the infectious period for inhabitants is
268 defined by the '*starting spread*' parameter from the disease submodel. The '*start sick leave*'
269 parameter defines when infected inhabitant agents stop commuting. After the '*duration of*
270 *infection*' has passed, the recovered inhabitants resume their daily mobility.

271 When inhabitant agents are infected, they are assumed to transmit the infection to the DW
272 particle agent. A wastewater particle is either infected or not infected. Not all appliance usage
273 leads to infected wastewater; for example, using a dishwasher does not transfer infection.
274 Only the use of toilet events produces infected wastewater. Recovered inhabitants may still
275 produce infected wastewater particles after recovery, as defined by the '*infected stool range*'
276 parameter.

277 **3.3. Spatiotemporal events**

278 Discrete events allow the detection of patterns at multiple spatiotemporal resolutions. For
279 instance, the DDW model enables the study of DW variability and anomalies at fine temporal
280 resolutions (minutes to hours) (which is crucial information during wastewater surveillance
281 sampling), and at a daily timestep allowing comparison of infected wastewater with disease
282 cases. All generated outputs are processed using R code scripts for the comparison of daily
283 disease cases and infected wastewater. The simulated discrete events (individual agent
284 actions) in time and space require a post-process to generate outputs fitted to an appropriate
285 data visualization. We define three postprocessing steps; each step represents an output
286 generated by multipled runs of the DDW model to guarantee consistent results.

287 1) The locality disease outbreak is the first generated raw output, and its post-processing
288 involves targeting the epidemic curves of the infected population and stool production
289 at a daily resolution. The locality disease data are used with the columns of date (with
290 daily timestamps), infected population, infected stool, infected stool after population
291 recovering, and run ID to differentiate between the simulations. The disease raw data
292 is retrieved from the actions of infected inhabitants and DW particle agents executed
293 at any location inside the simulated environment (locality level).

294 2) The second raw dataset is the locality mobility and the household disease spread data,
295 which produces a map series of infected inhabitants in households. The household
296 disease data include columns of date (with daily timestamps), household IDs, and
297 number of infected inhabitants, as well as run IDs to differentiate between the
298 simulations. It is retrieved at the end of each simulated day. The script also executes
299 temporal and spatial aggregation that adds the infected inhabitants given the

300 household IDs. The locality mobility data are recorded with the columns of date-time
301 (with hourly timestamps), number of inhabitants at home, and run IDs to differentiate
302 between the simulations. The mobility raw data are also retrieved from households,
303 and the R script produces a smoothed plot to show the mobility pattern of households
304 during the outbreak period from all simulations.

305

306 3) The sewer-infected wastewater is the third generated raw output and its post-
307 processing produces a map series of infected wastewater particles at maintenance
308 holes at three different temporal resolutions. The raw dataset includes date-time
309 columns (with minute timestamps), wastewater particle IDs, water appliances (to
310 identify the source of infected wastewater), the health statuses of inhabitants, and
311 run IDs to differentiate between the simulations. The third raw dataset is retrieved
312 from the actions of the infected DW particle agents at their arrival at a maintenance
313 hole in the sewer (catchment level). The R script filters the data for a given time range
314 and infected wastewater events. The script also performs temporal and spatial
315 aggregation, adding the infected wastewater events based on the maintenance holes
316 IDs for each target temporal resolution (6 minutes, 60 minutes, and 24 hours) for 25
317 runs.

318 **4. Use case: Disease outbreak**

319 We used the DDW for a COVID-19 use case to provide the disease spread and infected
320 wastewater outputs. The parameters for this use case are in Tables 1 and 2. All outputs are
321 derived from 25 simulation runs to ensure consistent results. We present three main outputs
322 of the model that confirm successful integration, each targeting a submodel:

- 323 • Disease outbreak: Four disease configuration outputs are delivered by varying the
324 transmission probabilities (β) and the Susceptible-Infected interactions (S) to verify
325 the DDW's consistency and the outbreak's behavior. The representation of COVID-19
326 used $\beta = 0.4$ and $S = 4$ for the simulation. The wastewater model considers the
327 prevalence of infected wastewater.
- 328 • Mobility: The outputs verify the model integration with the disease when analyzing
329 the variations in population mobility during the disease diffusion.
- 330 • Infected wastewater: The final output represents the integration of the three
331 submodels, as the infected wastewater variable can only be produced if the disease
332 and mobility models are integrated into the wastewater model.

333 **4.1. COVID-19 outbreak**

334 Figure 2 represents the integration between the disease spread generated by inhabitants'
335 interactions related to mobility. Figure 2 is a map series of disease spread and illustrates the
336 daily number of disease cases per household over 25 runs. The map series shows that the
337 outbreak range is approximately between 2022-03-22 and 2022-03-31. In most cases, there
338 is a daily infection average of 0.4 to 0.8 per household per run (or 10 to 20 infections per
339 household in 25 runs), with some outliers between 1.6 and 2 (or 40 to 50 infections per
340 household in 25 runs). It can also be observed that the southern area of the locality has a
341 higher infection density. High infection densities are largely explained by the significant
342 number of students infected during school interactions and returning home to their
343 respective neighborhood blocks, as indicated by the census data. The map series also allows
344 us to appreciate the outbreak's evolution, providing the spatial perspective absent in the
345 usual graph of an epidemic curve.

346 Figure 3 below shows the simulated time graphs of disease cases and wastewater infection
347 levels. The four experiments in rows a, b, c, and d were conducted in which the transmission
348 rate ' β ' (0.05, 0.1, 0.1, and 0.4) and the number of interactions ' S ' (1, 2, 4, 4) were varied. The
349 simulated outbreak from Figure 3-d defines the disease variables that represent a typical
350 COVID-19 outbreak. The first column from Figure 3 shows the generated infected stool and
351 assumes that the population keeps producing infected stool after recovery, a characteristic
352 of SARS-CoV-2 prevalence in the stool. The second column shows infected stool without
353 prolonged prevalence of infection in the stool after the agents have recovered. The last
354 column shows the count of infected inhabitant agents. The last column shows the count and
355 evolution of the infected population. Based on Figure 3, we evaluate: (1) simulation runs that
356 lead to so-called die-outs, where the disease does not spread; (2) the number of infected
357 inhabitants and the amount of infected stool; (3) the duration of the outbreak; and (4) the
358 shape of the epidemic curves.

359 Die-outs are represented in the figures as dots on the zero line. More die-outs are expected
360 with lower transmission rates (β) and fewer interactions (S) with other agents, reducing the
361 likelihood of an infected inhabitant agent transmitting the disease. Die-outs occur in
362 experiments a, b, and c but not in experiment d. The total number of accumulated infected
363 inhabitant agents varies across the four experiments (around 170, 270, 280, and 350,
364 respectively). This is reflected in peak values of 0–65 (experiment a), 0–100 (experiment b),
365 0–90 (experiment c) and 150–250 (experiment d). A similar pattern is observed for two
366 infected stool figures (with and without the extended duration of infectiousness). At the peak,
367 the values for experiments a through d are 0–95, 0–150, 0–125, and 190–250, respectively,
368 for extended infectiousness and 0–50, 0–85, 0–100, and 100–200, without extended
369 infectiousness.

370 In all experiments, the initial infections were introduced in March. The simulation is ended
371 when the outbreak no longer generates new infections. When considering the duration of the
372 outbreak, we see that the outbreak lasts until May 7 (around 47 days) for experiment a, until
373 April 18 (30 days) for experiment b, until May 7 (approximately 50 days) for experiment c, and
374 until April 8 for experiment d (20 days after the initial cases were introduced).

375 We also observe clear differences in the shape of the epidemic curve. With an increase in β
376 and S , the curves become shorter, and the peaks become higher. Notably, the difference in
377 curve shape between the infected stool with and without extended excretion is evident in
378 experiment d. Assuming that recovered inhabitant agents contribute to this value, the peak
379 is flattened, and high values are recorded over six days, compared to only three days in the
380 experiment without extended excretion. Rows in Figure 3.a, b, c, and d represent the different
381 transmission probabilities and the number of infected individuals. Figure 3.a shows that the
382 epidemic curves reduced to approximately 75 infected inhabitants at the outbreak peak. In
383 contrast, the duration of the outbreak spans three different months, differing from Figure 3.d,
384 which spans 20 days. A comparison between the rows of Figure 3 also shows that the disease
385 parameter β has a greater influence than the 'S' parameter in altering the epidemic curve
386 pattern. For instance, a comparison of 3.c and 3.d, with β values of 0.1 and 0.4, shows that
387 the outbreak peak reduces from 250 to 100 infected inhabitants. Figure 3 also verifies the
388 integration of the disease and infected wastewater production, as infected stool can only be
389 produced with the disease spreading.

390 **4.2. Mobility and COVID-19 spread**

391 Figure 4 shows the outbreak's peak pattern in the inhabitants' mobility. As inhabitants stay
392 home when getting infected, the number of people at home increases, generating the peak.
393 At the peak, we observe a decrease in mobility of approximately 60 infected agents (1660
394 agents at home versus 1600 at the start and end of the outbreak). After the peak, as
395 inhabitants recover from the disease, their mobility increases, leading to lower counts of
396 individuals at home. The synchrony between Figures 2 and 4 demonstrates the consistency
397 of the interactions between the submodels for the outbreak and inhabitants' mobility. This
398 interaction forms the basis for the subsequent production of infected wastewater, presented
399 as the model outputs in the following sections.

400 **4.3. Sewer infected wastewater**

401 Figure 5 shows the simulated infected wastewater particles at sewage maintenance holes at
402 a daily resolution. The map series consists of 16 days during the main period of the outbreak
403 with 24-hour intervals using disease variables $\beta = 0.4$ and $S = 4$. Each timestamp shows the
404 aggregated events from individual agent actions, revealing the emergent sewer pattern of
405 infected wastewater particles. The spatiotemporal heterogeneity distribution of the colored
406 circles reflects the accumulated flow of events in the main collectors, representing a sewer
407 pattern.

408 The temporal epidemic curve pattern of infected stool production when the inhabitants start
409 recovering (Figure 3.d) matches the daily increase of infected wastewater particles shown in
410 the map series from Figure 5. Both figures (Figures 3.d and 5) synchronize between March 26
411 and April 1, illustrating the spatiotemporal dynamics of infected wastewater particles,

412 particularly the prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 in recovered populations that still produce infected
413 stool.

414 Figure 6 shows the spatiotemporal heterogeneity of infected wastewater particles. The
415 results from Figure 6 are for a single day with 60-minute and 6-minute intervals. The time
416 stamps every 6 minutes from Figure 6.b preserve information from individual agent actions
417 and reveal the emergent sewer collector flow pattern of the infected wastewater particles.
418 The counts of infected wastewater particles peak at 120 to 140 infected wastewater events
419 per 6 minutes between 09:00 and 10:00. After 10:30, and there is a substantial decrease in
420 infected wastewater. The map series from Figure 6.a differentiates from Figure 6.b by using
421 hourly intervals between 8:00 and 11:00 instead of the 6-minute intervals. Figure 6.a shows
422 that the maximum number of infected wastewater events occur between 9:00 and 10:00
423 hours, with 500 and 600 events per hour from the sum of events of the 25 simulations.
424 Although the hourly intervals in Figure 6.a represent some spatiotemporal heterogeneity of
425 the sewage flow of infected events, the heterogeneity is considerably reduced compared to
426 Figure 6.b.

427 **5. Discussion**

428 In this paper, we focus on integrating agent-based disease, population mobility, and
429 wastewater models. While there is ABM literature about the three mentioned models, this
430 DDW ABM is the first attempt to integrate them and simultaneously simulate the
431 spatiotemporal dynamics of an outbreak and infected wastewater. The disease model
432 spreads the infection, where infected inhabitants transfer their health status to the produced
433 wastewater particles, allowing the identification of infected wastewater events across the
434 sewer. In this way, the DDW enables the comparison of the number of infected inhabitant
435 agents with the prevalence of a disease in wastewater at different spatial locations within the
436 sewer network.

437 The COVID-19 use case demonstrates the integration of the disease, mobility, and wastewater
438 models. The DDW model is not calibrated and validated for COVID-19 modeling. This is also
439 unnecessary, as the purpose of the use case is to demonstrate the integration of the
440 submodels and conduct experiments that show the potential of the model. An assessment of
441 the DDW outputs shows that the main spatiotemporal patterns match. First, the results of
442 the COVID-19 outbreak show epidemic curve patterns of infected populations comparable
443 with similar disease AMB models (Barat et al., 2021; Truszkowska et al., 2021). The outbreak
444 pattern outputs of the infected population demonstrate plot shapes similar to normal
445 distributions. Without extended excretion of the infection after recovery, the infected stool
446 production over time is correlated with the number of infected individuals. The extended
447 prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 leads to a curve with an extended peak comparable with the
448 literature (Randazzo et al., 2020; McManus et al., 2023). For instance, the extended
449 prevalence trend of SARS-CoV-2 in infected wastewater can be seen in plots measuring gc/l

450 over time in parallel with the infected population (Joseph-Duran et al., 2022). After an
451 outbreak, a predominantly flat concentration range is shown and reproduced in the DDW.
452 Second, the patterns between the mobility dynamics and the disease spread found in the
453 literature (Carteni et al., 2020; Badr et al., 2020) are also replicated in the DDW; as the number
454 of inhabitants that remain at home increases, the spread of the virus decreases. Finally, the
455 infected wastewater pattern in the map series across the sewer at a daily resolution matches
456 the epidemic curve pattern of the disease outbreak. The daily increase in the infected
457 population results in a similar increase in infected wastewater. As shown in the map series,
458 the pattern of infected wastewater across the sewer system also follows the flow network,
459 where most wastewater accumulates in the collectors, replicating the expected behavior.

460 Modeling at multiple temporal resolutions offers many benefits, including better detection of
461 patterns, which is key for ABM validation (Heppenstall et al., 2021b), particularly for applying
462 the DDW model to wastewater surveillance. Other studies have also confirmed that the
463 temporal and spatial resolutions affect model outputs (Evans and Kelley, 2004; Heppenstall
464 et al., 2021a). High or low resolutions may or may not be required for the DDW outputs,
465 depending on the target variable. For instance, a daily resolution is sufficient for the epidemic
466 curve to capture the pattern (Figure 3). However, an hourly resolution must be provided to
467 capture the pattern for population mobility since a daily resolution excludes population
468 commuting hours (Figure 4). Even more critically, capturing infected wastewater patterns
469 across the sewer requires multiple resolutions. Three infected wastewater map series during
470 the outbreak peak were presented with 6-minute, 60-minute, and 24-hour resolutions,
471 demonstrating that the model outputs at different resolutions can differ (Figures 5 and 6).
472 The DDW's ability to model outputs at different resolutions is of special relevance, as the

473 infected wastewater patterns were better revealed at a higher temporal resolution (6
474 minutes).

475 The DDW required a discrete event ABM approach to solve two major challenges and to
476 provide pathways for future model integrations. First, the temporal aggregation of agent
477 behavioral rules in the DDW model records individual agent actions in time and space.
478 Second, it overcomes the limited exploration of spatiotemporal heterogeneity at different
479 resolutions to facilitate the discovery of the hidden patterns of multiple variables, such as the
480 infected wastewater across the sewer. Although there are disease ABMs at high resolutions
481 (Mahdizadeh Gharakhanlou and Hooshangi, 2020; Truszkowska et al., 2021), they do not
482 consider individual and disaggregated agent events (or actions) and do not address the two
483 aforementioned challenges, which are key for explaining the spatiotemporal dynamics of
484 infected wastewater. A discrete ABM makes integrating features or submodels more feasible
485 and makes the DDW useful for studying different spatial and temporal patterns. For instance,
486 the design of the DDW makes it possible to include rainfall conditions as precipitation time
487 series or integrate hydrological submodels from similar ABMs (Augustijn et al., 2016).
488 Integrating more target variables, such as gene copies from other pathogens, is possible, but
489 this requires further research. In general, the DDW presents alternatives for modeling highly
490 variable or stochastic phenomena in time and space, which require considering more than a
491 single resolution where spatiotemporal heterogeneity is key.

492 The DDW has limitations as the current use case focuses on an exploratory model useful to
493 further our understanding of the disease spread linked to the production of infected
494 wastewater. The DDW is validated for total suspended solids (DelaPaz-Ruíz et al., 2023), the
495 main indicator for detecting stool in wastewater. Since the simulated disease outbreak and

496 infected stool represent a hypothetical use case in exploratory research, strict validation is
497 not required at this ABM stage (Heppenstall et al., 2021a). However, we recommend a follow-
498 up study with a larger case study so that there is sufficient calibration and validation data to
499 compare observed and simulated viral loads and TSS dynamics. The assessment of infected
500 wastewater patterns across the sewer also presents an opportunity for future study because
501 of the early state of the art in this field. The assessment of infected wastewater between
502 weekdays and weekends is out of the scope of this manuscript, but such differences should
503 be investigated. It is also important to note the challenge of modeling gene copies in the DDW,
504 which has not been developed but would be useful for direct validation of the relationship
505 between the simulated infected wastewater and wastewater surveillance samples.
506 Complementary to the output verifications, the disease and wastewater integration was
507 analyzed by changing the disease variables, demonstrating the behavior of an outbreak when
508 increasing and decreasing the transmission probabilities of COVID-19. The DDW is an
509 unsophisticated simulation, and the submodels are based on simple rules and statistics that
510 can be handy for simplifying the complexities of modeling disease and wastewater. The
511 population mobility submodel is an example of the simplified rules, where the commute of
512 inhabitants depends on the availability of census data. Commuting into and out of the study
513 area is not simulated.

514 The DDW shows a solid integration of disease, mobility, and wastewater, which previous
515 studies have not addressed. The DDW shows consistent patterns between the interactions of
516 the integrated models and has potential for future improvement and applicability. The DDW
517 differentiates itself from related models by providing sophisticated map series with details on
518 spatiotemporal heterogeneity at multiple resolutions. We have used an outbreak case for
519 COVID-19; however, another disease can be targeted by modifying the disease input

520 parameters. Alternatively, the use of medication or drugs could also be modeled. The DDW
521 has future applications, for instance, in wastewater epidemiology (and surveillance), to model
522 pathogens or other substances found in stool and urine that are potentially detectable from
523 wastewater samples.

524 **6. Conclusions**

525 This study advances wastewater-based epidemiology by proposing an event-based ABM
526 model integrating diseases, population mobility, and wastewater, which can be used to model
527 various diseases. An existing wastewater ABM was extended by integrating the disease and
528 mobility models to allow combined analysis of disease outbreaks and infected wastewater. A
529 discrete event approach was used to deal with the differences in temporal resolutions of the
530 individual models. The integrated model improves the representation of spatiotemporal
531 heterogeneity at multiple resolutions for diseases and wastewater, making it easier to
532 uncover patterns.

533 Through an outbreak use case applied to COVID-19, we demonstrated that the integrated
534 model produces trends and patterns compatible with findings from the current literature. The
535 epidemic curve shows the expected outbreak patterns of four disease scenarios at a daily
536 resolution. The spread of the disease is presented as a map series at a daily resolution,
537 showing the number of infections in households linked to the mobility pattern, which requires
538 an hourly resolution. The outbreak evolution demonstrates the expected behavior of a
539 disease. The infected wastewater outputs at the sewer maintenance holes are presented as
540 a map series using multiple resolutions (6 minutes, 60 minutes, and 24 hours). The sewer
541 outputs differ between resolutions, highlighting the relevance of modeling at different

542 resolutions for highly variable phenomena. The discrete event ABM approach can also be
543 beneficial for modeling other diseases or stochastic spatiotemporal phenomena. Our future
544 work will focus on using the integrated model to enhance the sampling methodology used by
545 wastewater surveillance monitoring networks.

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707 **9. Title of tables and figures**

708 **Table 1.** Parameters of the disease model (e.g., for a COVID-19 use case).

709 **Table 2.** Entities of the DDW model. Modified from [22].

710 **Table 3.** Supplementary material. ODD entities of the DDW model. Modified from [22].

711 **Table 4.** Supplementary material. Description of attributes (or states variables).

712 **Table 5.** Supplementary material. Required input data for the DDW.

713

714 **Figure 1.** Representing the modular links between the submodels.

715 **Figure 2.** Mapping the density of infected inhabitants at households over time.

716 **Figure 3.** Epidemic curves of simulated outbreaks for the population and infected stool.

717 **Figure 4.** Mobility pattern of the count of inhabitants at home during an outbreak.

718 **Figure 5.** Example of simulated infected wastewater particles at sewage maintenance holes
719 at a daily resolution.

720 **Figure 6.** Differences between resolutions of infected wastewater particles at sewage
721 maintenance holes.

722 **Figure 7.** Supplementary material. Essential procedures linking the DDW discrete event ABM.

723

724 **10. Tables**725 **Table 1.** *Parameters of the disease model (e.g., for a COVID-19 use case).*

Parameter	Initial value	Description
Duration of simulation	30 days	The ABM will run for one month.
Contact rate	10%	Chance of an inhabitant agent contacting other inhabitants.
Disease status	Susceptible	Susceptible, Infected, or Recovered
Susceptible-Infected interactions (S)	4	Maximum range of new possible infections produced by a single infected inhabitant (S).
Starting spread	2 days	Days after an infected inhabitant starts spreading the disease
Starting sick leave	1 day	Days after an infection takes place, the inhabitant stops executing mobility.
Infected stool range	2–3 weeks	Weeks that an inhabitant keeps producing infected stool after recovering.
No. initial infected cases (N)	5 individuals	Randomly assigned in the population.
Transmission rate (β)	1.25	The average value of the range [0.3 – 2.2], (β).
Recovery rate (γ)	0.2	The recovery rate is 1/infection duration.
Duration of infection (D)	5 days	Days that an inhabitant may infect others.
Secondary cases (I)	0 individual	Infection cases that are not initial.

726

Table 2. Entities of the DDW model. Modified from (DelaPaz-Ruiz et al., 2023).

Entity	Variable	Description	Possible value	Units
Inhabitants	Age	Age category	18–24	-
	Study	Attend school	Yes	-
	Health	Health status	Infected	-
	Infection time	Date and time of infection	21-03-2022, 10:30:00	-
	Transmission type	Initial or secondary transmission	Secondary	-
	School level	School level	Highschool	-
	Work	Actively working	Yes	-
	Gender	Inhabitant sex	Female	-
	CVEGEO	Block location (geographic ID)	1302700010105004	-
	Ind ID	Individual ID	01750	-
	Location	Current location	Home, school, work	-
	Education level	Education grade	2	-
DW particle	DW type	Type of water appliance	Toilet stool	-
	Disease	Health condition	Infected	-
	Infection time	Date and time of infection	21-03-2022, 10:30:00	-
	DW quantity	DW liters	9	l
	DW quality	DW pollutants: COD and TSS	453	mg/l
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	-
	Ind id	Individual ID	01750	-
	DW speed	Traveling particle speed	1.8	m/s
	Traveling path	Sewage network node	Node 2020	-
Houses	House id	House ID	304	-
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	-
Blocks	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	-
Economic points	ID	Economic point ID	7996840	-
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	-
	Avg. workers	Average workers	3, 5, 15....	-
	School exists	School in this point	High school	-

Sewage network	Node	Connecting nodes	Node 11	-
	Travel path	Path to move DW particle	Node 684	-
Treatment plant	Final station	The final destination of the traveling path	-	-

727

728

729 **11. Figures**

730

Figure 1. Representing the modular links between the submodels.

731

Figure 2. Mapping the density of infected inhabitants at households over time. The figure represents the sum of 25 simulations showing robust results and highlighting the spatial heterogeneity of the households. Disease variables $\beta = 0.4$, and $S = 4$ are used.

732

Figure 3. Epidemic curves of simulated outbreaks for the population and infected stool. The stool columns differentiate between infected stool with and without considering whether the recovered population continues to produce infected stool. Rows a, b, c, and d represent four simulations with different combinations of transmission probabilities (β) and the maximum number of possible inhabitants that can be infected (S). Each scenario is run 25 times to ensure stable results.

734

Figure 4. Mobility pattern of the count of inhabitants at home during an outbreak. The mobility pattern shows the increase of inhabitants remaining at home during the days of the outbreak (2022-03-23 to 2022-03-31), which synchronizes with Figure 2.

735

Figure 5. Example of simulated infected wastewater particles at sewage maintenance holes at a daily resolution. Map series with 24-hour interval during the outbreak period from 25 simulations showing the daily transition of the number of infected particles. Disease variables $\beta=0.4$, and $S=4$ are used.

Figure 6. Differences between resolutions of infected wastewater particles at sewage maintenance holes. a) Map series with a 60-minute interval during the peak outbreak hour from 25 simulations showing the hourly transition of the number of particles. b) Map series with 06-minute interval during the peak outbreak from 25 simulations showing the transition of the number of particles in short time intervals. Disease variables $\beta = 0.4$, and $S = 4$ are used.

739

740

741

742 **12. Supplementary material**

743 The repository to reproduce results (DelaPaz-Ruíz et al., 2024) is openly available in the
744 following link: <https://github.com/delapazruiz/abm.disease.mobility.wastewater>

745 **12.1. ODD protocol**

746 In the following, the Overview, Design concepts, Details (ODD) protocol template (Railsback
747 and Ayllón, 2020) has been adapted to provide a structured description of the DDW model.
748 The purpose of the ODD is to provide transparency and information regarding the
749 functionality of the model.

750 12.1.1. Purpose and patterns

751 The DDW model is an aid designed for wastewater disease monitoring, aiming to model
752 disease spread and mobility along with the dynamics of infected domestic wastewater (DW)
753 across space and time based on the simulation of human behavior. Applications include
754 planning wastewater sampling (location and time) and translating sampling results to various
755 disease cases. We address the question: How does modeling aid in understanding the
756 spatiotemporal dynamics of infected domestic wastewater? The model is generic and can be
757 easily applied to other diseases. The results can be generated at multiple temporal resolutions
758 due to its event-based setup. The DDW reproduces realistic epidemic and DW patterns, and
759 we have used the widely known patterns for the epidemic curves of the infected populations
760 for the diseases. The model also reproduces pollutant patterns, such as total suspended solids
761 (TSS). The spatiotemporal DW patterns are represented by day-to-day human activities at
762 specific hours.

763 12.1.2. Entities, state variables, and scales

764 The DDW consists of the following entities: a) agents representing inhabitants and DW
765 particles, b) the environment consisting of houses, neighborhood blocks, schools, economic
766 points, a sewer network, and a treatment plant. The information characterizing these entities
767 is listed in Table 3, which has been adapted from DelaPaz-Ruíz et al. (DelaPaz-Ruíz et al., 2023)
768 to include the entities related to the disease submodel. The model runs dynamic time steps
769 on the locality for two weeks, where inhabitants' actions are based on discrete event
770 simulations. Table 4 develops the attributes of the entities.

Table 3. Supplementary material. ODD entities of the DDW model. Modified from (DelaPaz-Ruiz et al., 2023).

Entity	Variable	Description	Possible value	Data type
Inhabitants	Age	Age category	18–24	String
	Study	Attend school	Yes	String
	Health	Health status	Susceptible	String
	Infection time	Date and time of infection	21-03-2022, 10:30:00	Time stamp
	Transmission type	Initial or secondary transmission	Secondary	String
	School level	School level	Highschool	String
	Work	Actively working	Yes	Boolean
	Gender	Inhabitant sex	Female	String
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	Integer
	Ind ID	Individual ID	01750	Integer
	Location	Current location	Home, school, work	String
	Education level	Education grade	2	Integer
DW particle	DW type	Type of water appliance	Toilet stool	String
	Disease	Health condition	Infected	String
	Infection time	Date and time of infection	21-03-2022, 10:30:00	Time stamp
	DW quantity	DW liters	9	Numeric
	DW quality	DW pollutants: COD and TSS	453	Integer
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	Integer
	Ind id	Individual ID	01750	Integer
	DW speed	Traveling particle speed	1.8	Numeric
	Traveling path	Sewage network node	2020	Integer
Houses	House id	House ID	304	Integer
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	Integer
Blocks	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	Integer
Economic points	ID	Economic point ID	7996840	Integer
	CVEGEO	Block location	1302700010105004	Integer
	Avg. workers	Average workers	3, 5, 15	Integer
	School exists	School in this point	High school	String

Sewage network	Node	Connecting nodes	11	Integer
	Travel path	Node path to move DW particle	684	Integer
Treatment plant	Final station	The final destination of the traveling path	-	Integer

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Table 4. *Supplementary material. Description of attributes (or states variables).*

Entity	Variable	Change over time	Further description
Inhabitants	Age	Static	Differentiates calculation of pollutant loads and probabilities of water usage between age groups.
	Study	Static	Identifies which inhabitants attend schools.
	Health	Dynamic	Tracks health status changes during commuting.
	Infection time	Dynamic	Records the timestamp of health status changes according to the SIR model execution.
	Transmission type	Dynamic	Records the type of health status change according to the SIR model execution.
	School level	Static	Assigns inhabitants to their respective educational level locations (e.g., elementary school).
	Work	Static	Identifies which inhabitants are actively working.
	Gender	Static	Differentiates calculation of pollutant loads and probabilities of water usage by gender.
	CVEGEO	Static	Assigns inhabitants in their respective neighborhood.
	Ind ID	Static	Differentiates and tracks events by individual ID.
	Location	Dynamic	Tracks inhabitants' location changes during commuting.
	Education level	Static	Provides additional detail complementary to school level.
DW particle	DW type	Dynamic	Stores and differentiates the water appliance sources for the calculation of pollutant loads and events with viral concentrations (i.e., stool, and urine).
	Disease	Dynamic	Stores and differentiates the health status based on the inhabitant that generated the water appliance event (i.e., infected or recovered).
	Infection time	Dynamic	Stores the infection timestamp based on the infected inhabitant that generated the water appliance event.
	DW quality	Dynamic	Stores the pollutant load value. Calculated after postprocessing.
	CVEGEO	Static	Stores the CVEGEO location of the inhabitants in their respective neighborhoods.

	Ind ID	Static	Differentiates and track inhabitants' events by their ID.
	DW speed	Static	Defines the average movement speed of wastewater particles.
	Traveling path	Static	Guides wastewater particles according to the sewer direction.
Houses	House id	Static	Allocates inhabitant agents to households.
	CVEGEO	Static	Differentiates households by their neighborhood block IDs.
Blocks	CVEGEO	Static	Differentiates the neighborhood block IDs.
Economic points	ID	Static	Differentiates between economic points and commute inhabitants at school or work locations.
	CVEGEO	Static	To differentiate economic points between the neighborhood block IDs.
	Avg. workers	Static	Defines the allowed number of inhabitants at the economic point.
	School exists	Static	Differentiates between school locations and the economic points.
Sewage network	Node	Static	Differentiates between the maintenance holes.
	Travel path	Static	Guides wastewater particles based on the sewer directions.
Treatment plant	Final station	Static	Identifies the final station for the motion of wastewater.

772 The DDW model facilitates simulation and representation of multiple spatial and temporal
773 resolutions. The model uses the NetLogo time extension, which defines a time step as one
774 hour. The duration of the simulation is defined by a specific time stamp. However, a maximum
775 range of two months is sufficient to represent the integration of the disease outbreak,
776 mobility, and wastewater production. The input data shapefiles loaded in Netlogo defines the
777 model's spatial scale.

778 The discrete event ABM is suitable for modeling highly variable spatiotemporal heterogeneity
779 with detailed resolutions. This suitability arises from the ability of discrete events to fully
780 represent individual behavior, which eliminates concerns about selecting an adequate
781 granularity for agent events over spatiotemporal scales. Discrete events allow the detection

782 of potential unknown patterns of a phenomenon's behavior that are otherwise undetectable
783 when multiple spatiotemporal resolutions are unavailable. For instance, focusing on
784 spatiotemporal heterogeneity in the DDW enables the study of variability and anomalies,
785 which is crucial during wastewater surveillance sampling to track the production of infected
786 wastewater at specific times and locations. Figure 7 shows essential interactions between the
787 discrete event ABM procedures of the submodels. The ABM procedures cover the
788 relationships between mobility, disease, and wastewater. Interactions are shown in Figure 7
789 as procedures that are on the edges of two submodels (represented by two different colors).
790 For instance, the procedure 'set DW particle status' represents a transition from the disease
791 to the wastewater submodel by considering the health condition of the inhabitants, which is
792 further transmitted to the DW particle.

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Figure 7. Supplementary material. Essential procedures linking the DDW discrete event ABM. The DDW procedures are linked between the submodels, where the agent actions are conditioned to spatial and temporal conditions for executing the individual agent events.

798 12.1.3. Design concepts

799 *Basic principles*

800 The DDW model extends the traditional domestic wastewater (DW) ABM by integrating a
801 disease outbreak based on the Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) model. The DDW also
802 integrates a population mobility model, which is essential for triggering the interactions
803 between inhabitant agents and the spread of the disease in the locality. When inhabitant
804 agents commute to school or work, they produce wastewater particle agents. Wastewater
805 particles are produced by inhabitant agents via water appliances. Wastewater agents
806 simulate the flow of sewage and store the health status of the inhabitant agents, allowing for
807 the definition of the production of infected stool and the tracking of infected wastewater
808 particles in time and space across the sewer network. Disease spread is activated when an
809 infected inhabitant interacts with a susceptible inhabitant in the same location (e.g., school)
810 and randomly infects the other inhabitants (see the disease model section). Inhabitants stop
811 commuting when infected until they recover but continue producing wastewater particles
812 reflecting the ongoing health status of these inhabitants.

813 *Emergence*

814 Emergence occurs through the simultaneous combination of the DDW submodels. Depending
815 on the spatial configuration of the locality's environment and interactions between inhabitant
816 agents, two main targeted spatiotemporal patterns emerge. The first is the epidemic curve
817 pattern generated by the spread of the disease at specific locations among the inhabitant
818 agents. The rules governing susceptible, infected, and recovered states are associated with
819 this emergence. The second emerging pattern is related to the infected wastewater particle
820 agents. This emergence is visualized as sewer flow where particles accumulate. The count of

821 infected particles increases and decreases as the disease spreads. The relevant rules
822 associated with this phenomenon include the flow motion in the sewer network, the disease
823 spread that transmitting the health condition of inhabitants, and the prolonged prevalence
824 of infected particles in the recovered population.

825 *Interactions*

826 Inhabitant agents interact with a random subset of other agents to facilitate disease spread.
827 Two types of interaction groups exist: household members (other inhabitant agents living in
828 the same house) and interactions at school or work. The 'S' parameter dictates the number
829 of other agents with whom interaction takes place. The model does not simulate interactions
830 between infected, susceptible, and recovered inhabitants indiscriminately; it restricts
831 interactions to those between infected and susceptible inhabitant agents. Interactions are
832 generated via random sampling. When infected and susceptible inhabitants are located at the
833 same location, a human-to-human interaction function $\mathcal{F}(HH)$ activates, generating the
834 infections.

835 The $\mathcal{F}(HH)$ is linked to mobility, meaning that it is executed twice daily for all inhabitants
836 who move or have the 'infected' status: once when inhabitants travel to school and work, and
837 once when they return home. The interaction is defined by the 'S' parameter range, which
838 indicates how many possible agents an infected agent has contact with resulting in infection.

839 A transmission rate ' β ' is used to define the probability of infecting a susceptible inhabitant. The range
840 'S' of agents is sampled randomly from the locations that an infected agent visits (household,
841 school, workplace). When the infected and susceptible condition is met, the infected
842 inhabitant is assumed to interact with a given number of other random inhabitants in the
843 same location ('S').

844 The NetLogo/Java script of the $\mathcal{F}(HH)$ is as follows:

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845 Let target one-of other inhabitants-here with [Disease_state = "Infected"]
846   if random-float 1 < 'β' [
847     let mylist.of.new.infections (range 'S' 0 -1)
848     repeat one-of mylist.of.new.infections [
849       get-sick
850       set transmissionType "Secondary"]
851   ]

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852 The mathematical expression of $\mathcal{F}(HH)$ is as follows. Let:

- 853 • I be the set of inhabitants at the current location.
- 854 • $I_{\text{infected}} \subset I$ be the subset of infected inhabitants.
- 855 • $\beta_{\text{transmission}}$ be the transmission probability.
- 856 • S be the range of possible infections from an inhabitant, which can be expressed as a
- 857 list.
- 858 • T be the transmission type, initially "Primary" but changing to "Secondary" upon
- 859 transmission.

Step 1. Select a target: $target \in I_{\text{infected}}$ (1)

Step 2. Probability check: $If \text{Random float} \in [0,1) < \beta_{\text{transmission}}, \text{ then}$ (2)

Step 3. List and repeat actions (create $mylist = S$, $mylist$, and iterate the actions for each element): $For \text{ randomly selected elements in } mylist, \{Perform \text{ get - sick: Set transmission to "Secondary"}\}$ (3)

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861 In summary, the mathematical expression of $\mathcal{F}(HH)$ can be broken down into the following

862 steps to capture the essence of the $\mathcal{F}(HH)$ interaction in a mathematical framework: The

863 selection of a random infected inhabitant set of current inhabitants. A subsequent check of

864 whether a random number drawn from a distribution $[0, 1)$ is less than the transmission
865 probability. Then, if the probability check is satisfied, a range list is created and the infection
866 process is repeated for one randomly selected element from this list, setting the transmission
867 type to "Secondary".

868 *Observation*

869 The observation in the DDW records every agent event as the target variable of the retrieved
870 patterns of each submodel. For every inhabitant agent, it records the execution timestamp
871 (i.e., when they infect or move), location (house ID, school, work location), and health status
872 (susceptible, infected, recovered). For every wastewater agent, it records the execution
873 timestamp (e.g., the arrival at a maintenance hole), location (manholes and inhabitant IDs),
874 and source descriptive information from the agent that generated the wastewater (e.g., such
875 as use of a water appliance emitting urine or stool, and health status such as susceptible,
876 infected, or recovered). The number of infected inhabitant agents per day is observed for the
877 disease model. The count of inhabitants that remain at home during the outbreak evolution
878 indicates mobility. The count of infected wastewater particles, including their arrival at a
879 specific location in the sewer system (maintenance holes), is observed for the infected
880 wastewater.

881 *Stochasticity*

882 The number of inhabitant agents per neighborhood block is fixed; however, their distribution
883 among households within the blocks is randomized. The inhabitants loaded into the ABM
884 have individual census information, which assigns them to their respective school activities.
885 The agents are randomly located at an economic point for work activities. Stochasticity is also

886 present in wastewater variability, which fluctuates depending on the time of day and the
887 presence of individuals in specific locations. Domestic water usage and the dynamics of
888 emerging pollutant loads are modeled as probabilistic events to represent the inherent
889 variability of DW loads.

890 12.1.4. Initialization

891 A simulation starts with loading the environments (locality, houses, economic points, schools,
892 sewer pipes, maintenance holes, and treatment plant.). Then, the synthetic inhabitants
893 generated via spatial microsimulation are loaded into the ABM and assigned to houses based
894 on their location ID from the census data. Spatial microsimulation provides individual census
895 data that allow the ABM to assign agents to their corresponding schools or economic location
896 to represent work activities. At the start of the simulation, all inhabitant agents are
897 susceptible. The disease submodel starts with five randomly infected individuals (inhabitant
898 agents). The wastewater submodel includes the release of wastewater particles after
899 initialization.

900 12.1.5. Input data

901 Table 5 lists the input data used in the DDW. The DDW uses geographical census data
902 produced by the federal authorities of Mexico (INEGI, the National Institute of Statistic and
903 Geography). There are two census datasets: one for economic activities (INEGI-DENUE, 2017)
904 and another for the population (INEGI, 2020). The census data also include the geographical
905 boundaries of the locality, neighborhood blocks, and number of houses in each block. The
906 household data were digitized using census information and satellite images.

907 The list of inhabitants was produced using spatial microsimulation (Lovelace and Dumont,
908 2018). Survey information related to the sewer network was digitized via a dedicated field

909 data collection exercise in 2022, and included pipework, maintenance holes, and the
 910 treatment plant. This was supported by liaising with the local authorities to verify as much as
 911 possible the connectivity of the network connectivity. We used topographic data from a
 912 digital elevation model based on SRTM Tiles for digitization, which were acquired via the
 913 NASA Server QGIS plugin (Duester, 2021) and the Drinking Water, Sewerage and Sanitation
 914 Manual (CONAGUA, 2019) applicable to Mexico.

915 *Table 5. Supplementary material. Required input data for the DDW.*

Files	Notes	Types
Census: Locality	Polygon area	Shp
Census: Neighborhood blocks	Multiple polygon areas	Shp
Census: Economic data	Multiple points	Shp
Census: Households	Multiple points	Shp
Census: List of inhabitants	Refers to the spatial microsimulation	CSV
Survey: Maintenance holes	Multiple points	Shp
Survey: Sewer network	Multiple lines	Shp
Survey: Treatment plant	Point	Shp

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